

The NEA Nuclear Data Processing Pipeline Supporting the JEFF-4.0 Nuclear Data Library Release

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ABSTRACT

The JEFF-4.0 nuclear data library was released in 2025, culminating 8 years of effort to create the most comprehensive dataset to date, covering a broad range of isotopes, nuclear reactions and nuclear application cases. The JEFF-4 project has benefited from the Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA) Data Bank efforts towards the modernisation of the nuclear data and software management. Several test versions of the JEFF-4 library have been curated and assessed via the NEA GitLab-based Data/DevOps environment, using data repositories to manage version control of the data. The pipelines dedicated to nuclear data processing, verification and validation are entirely reproducible and transparent, ensuring that changes, impact analyses and results are adequately preserved and traceable. As a result, the release of the JEFF-4.0 nuclear data library was accompanied by a variety of nuclear datasets produced by the NEA pipeline, that enable its use by several nuclear computational codes and supported by the new data management platform that ensures long-term data preservation.

Keywords: Nuclear Data, Nuclear Data Processing, JEFF-4.0, Data Management

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear energy has always relied on high-quality data, from basic physics quantities that underpin reactor physics to experimental benchmarks to validate safety margins. The quality and reliability of data form a cornerstone of scientific confidence and ultimately, public trust. International expectations in governance, quality standards and processes, engineering and architecture, integration and interfaces have changed significantly. Such changes have accelerated in recent years with the rise of data-hungry artificial intelligence (AI) applications and global momentum in open science and open data communities that are reshaping the standards for how data is curated, validated, licensed and disseminated.

The NEA Data Bank has modernized the way nuclear data and software are managed, verified and distributed, drawing on international best practices. This modernization program includes continuous integration, digital identifiers and machine-readable access through application programming interfaces (APIs). The goal is to preserve the scientific rigor that has defined data and benchmark evaluation for decades, while enabling new forms of collaboration and innovation to support novel technologies being deployed by our member countries.

The recent release of the Joint Evaluated Fission and Fusion (JEFF) library, built upon a Data/DevOps environment leveraging containerized and reproducible quality processes, deployed to a new research

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data management platform, marks a milestone in our modernization effort. This is part of a broad strategy to build an ecosystem where evaluated data, benchmarks and nuclear modeling software are seamlessly integrated, accessible, and ready to support a new generation of nuclear technologies, including through the application of machine learning and AI.

The JEFF-4.0 nuclear data library was released in 2025 and represents the culmination of nearly 8 years of effort to overhaul data development processes while creating the most comprehensive set of data to date, covering a broad range of isotopes, nuclear reactions and nuclear application cases. These data are essential for calculations in reactor design, safety analysis, criticality assessment, radiation shielding, fuel cycle studies and other cases where accuracy and reliability are required.

In terms of data infrastructure and management, what distinguishes JEFF-4.0 from previous versions created over the past 40 years is the way it was built. The library was developed within a Data/DevOps environment [1], using data repositories to manage version control of the data, all processes, benchmarks, and the software and experimental data used in those benchmarks. The pipelines that carry out these tasks are entirely reproducible and transparent, with test results and verification checks stored alongside the data. This ensures that changes, impact analyses and results are preserved and traceable so that downstream users can build upon data with confidence and future generations can easily build upon the work of their predecessors.

The JEFF-4.0 GitLab environment is tightly integrated with the NEA Nuclear Science Committee's international benchmark experiment databases, including the International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) [2], the International Reactor Physics Experiment Evaluation Project (IR-PhE) [3], and the Shielding Integral Benchmark Archive and Database (SINBAD) [4]. By embedding software-ready model repositories in the same environment, downstream users can access all relevant resources in one place. In cases where export controlled or licensed content is required, they are separated with role-based access managed by the Data Bank Computer Program Service team, which issues licenses and account access in compliance with data and code owner agreements.

This paper presents both the JEFF-4.0 nuclear data library contents and the current status of the NEA processing pipeline that has supported the development of the JEFF-4 project, providing standardized processing, verification, and validation of nuclear data.

2. THE JEFF-4.0 NUCLEAR DATA LIBRARY

The JEFF-4.0 nuclear data library [5] combines the available experimental and theoretical knowledge of nuclear reactions and nuclear decay in standard-format nuclear data files that ensure service to a wide user community. Thus, JEFF-4.0 has been released as a general-purpose library aiming to cover a variety of nuclear domains beyond nuclear energy and nuclear fusion, including space and earth exploration, medical applications, and nuclear science.

Released in June 2025, JEFF-4.0 brings several major updates on the neutron-induced reaction data after a comprehensive re-evaluation process. Nonetheless, it also provides revisited fission yields, proton-induced reaction data, and radioactive decay data. Following up the release of JEFF-3.3 library [6] in 2017, JEFF-4.0 results from a project that involved several test library versions that underwent rigorous study by the experts involved in the JEFF project and were efficiently managed by means of the NEA nuclear data pipeline [1].

Regarding the neutron-induced reaction data provided by JEFF-4.0, significant differences can be found compared to JEFF-3.3 library. Firstly, major actinides U-235, U-238 and Pu-239 were completely revisited in the resonance and fast energy regions, where new physics models were implemented. Given the current relevance of the Th-U fuel cycle, several updates were also introduced for Th-232 and U-233 isotopes. Concerning other areas of interest such as spent fuel management, waste reprocessing and transmutation scenarios, the minor actinides U-236, Np-237, Np-238, Pu-238, Pu-240, Pu-241, Pu-242, Am-241, and Am-243 were conveniently re-assessed. The developments on the fission product data are

tightly supported by the TENDL library, where thermal and resolved resonance regions were reviewed and updated. Those new evaluations were adopted in JEFF-4.0, ensuring a better performance for fission energy, fusion activation and decay heat applications. A similar approach was applied for a wide variety of isotopes, involving structural materials, coolants, and absorbers. This was achieved through a close collaboration with the INDEN project [7]. Likewise, a detailed evaluation led to the adoption of several files from JENDL-4.0 [8], JENDL-5.0 [9] and ENDF/B-VIII.1 [10] libraries. Additionally, JEFF-4.0 integrates a set of evaluated files from TENDL-2023 library [11] for those isotopes for which no evaluation was previously provided. This integration also includes files from the TENDL-2025 beta library, released in February 2025. Then, JEFF-4.0 library provided neutron-induced reaction data for a set of 2855 nuclides [12], supporting its application for a wide range of nuclear areas.

The JEFF-4.0 fission yields sub-library [13, 14] corresponds to the JEFF-3.3 sub-library but incorporates new evaluations of the thermal neutron-induced fission yields for U-233, U-235, Pu-239, and Pu-241. A completely new methodology was applied in that re-evaluation, involving new measurements at the Lohengrin spectrometer and a new treatment of the full experimental database. As a result, JEFF-4.0 has been proven to perform better for reactor burn-up calculations and spent fuel characterization.

The JEFF-4.0 thermal-neutron scattering law (TSL) sub-library [15] brings a substantially expanded dataset compared to previous versions, providing data for the elements of 84 materials, of which 24 in elemental form and 60 compounds. Evaluations of key reactor materials have been performed, including U and O in UO_2 , Pu and O in PuO_2 , Th and O in ThO_2 , and Zircaloy (Zy-4). Overall, the JEFF-4.0 TSL sub-library was built with 36 elements prepared in the frame of the JEFF project, with 16 files that were not provided by JEFF-3.3. A new evaluation for the relevant case of hydrogen in water (H in H_2O) has been prepared, along with updates in other 6 files. The sub-library was completed with 31 evaluations from ENDF/B-VIII.1 library and 65 evaluations from the NJOY+NCrystal library [16].

Minor updates were incorporated to the JEFF-4.0 sub-library for decay data [17] compared to JEFF-3.3 library. 8 radionuclides (Rb-93, Y-96, Y-96m, Y-99, Tc-103, Tc-108, I-138, and Cs-142) were revisited with new Total Absorption Gamma-ray Spectroscopy (TAGS) data while minor corrections were introduced in the Tc-99 and Am-242 evaluations.

JEFF-4.0 library is completed with the sub-libraries related to charged particles-induced reactions, which are largely based on TENDL-2023 data, namely proton-, alpha-, photon-, deuteron-, triton- and helion-induced reactions. Nonetheless, a proton-induced reactions dataset is provided for 288 stable nuclides, for which a thorough review has been carried out comparing and selecting evaluations from TENDL-2023, JENDL-5.0, and ENDF/B-VIII.1 libraries. In addition, the PADF-2 activation data were integrated in the selected evaluations allowing a better description of the available experimental data.

3. RECENT UPDATES ON THE NEA PROCESSING PIPELINE

The NEA processing pipeline was initially conceived and developed by [1] with the aim of supporting the JEFF project, ensuring the long-term storage and maintenance of data in a transparent, accessible and usable way. Providing the JEFF community with reproducible, high-quality data was the key objective, including the automation of nuclear data processing routines to the greatest extent possible. To achieve this, the NEA Data Bank developed a new framework based on GitLab, a web-based distributed Version Control System. GitLab facilitates the collaborative work on the evaluated nuclear data files while maintaining a comprehensive record of changes, aligned with the transparency and traceability principles.

As described in [1], the initial NEA processing pipeline incorporated various nuclear data verification tools, succeeded by the essential processing routines that produce the files usable by transport codes. This pipeline has been under continuous development and new capabilities have been added to support a wider range of applications and computational tools. Figure 1 depicts the current flowchart of the

NEA nuclear data processing pipeline supporting the JEFF developments.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the NEA nuclear data processing pipeline.

The GitLab framework has been restructured into a single repository that collects all JEFF evaluations and centralizes the processing pipeline, which can process a single isotope or the entire library. This allows the users to test the evaluated files in an independent way, better handle merge requests, and track issues.

The evaluated nuclear data files firstly undergo a **format verification** stage, including CHECKR, FIZCON, PSYCHE, endf-parserpy and ENDFtk utilities. While CHECKR, FIZCON, and PSYCHE were already included in the original pipeline [1], endf-parserpy [18] and ENDFtk [19] have been recently added. Overall, verification utilities provide feedback on the correctness and internal consistency of the evaluated files. This provides valuable information to nuclear data evaluators when updates are implemented into an evaluation. As a result, the pipeline produces a detailed report on the success rate of the performed format verification tests.

After the format verification, the pipeline proceeds to the **basic processing** stage in a different way depending on the evaluation type, isotope or TSL. Regarding the isotopes, preparatory processing routines are carried out using the NJOY nuclear data processing code [20]. NJOY_293K and NJOY_basics deal with the format conversion, resonance cross section reconstruction, Doppler broadening, effective self-shielded cross section generation, point-wise heat production cross section, radiation damage energy computation, and the addition of gas production reactions at 293.6 K and elevated temperatures, respectively. PENDF files produced at this stage are essential for the next stages. Additionally, NJOY_dragr has been recently implemented to support Dragon lattice physics code [21] for core simulations via the generation of the DRAGLIB format multi-group datasets.

The **basic processing** stage related to TSL evaluations involves both NJOY and AMPX [22] processing codes, that generate ACE- and AMPX-format processed files at all available temperatures. TSL evaluations are bound to a reference isotope, which is automatically retrieved from the isotope repository. Several improvements have been recently implemented into the TSL NJOY processing routines to accommodate different evaluation methodologies, automatically retrieving the information from the evaluated TSL file. The ACE-format files support the use of the library by continuous-energy Monte Carlo codes such as MCNP or Serpent, while the AMPX-format library is intended for use in the SCALE Code System [23]. Likewise, TSL evaluations are also processed into the DRAGLIB format, which are collated into a single file with the rest of DRAGLIB files.

The basic processing stage for an isotope is completed by the **other formats** stage with the following nuclear data processing utilities:

- AMPX, which enables the use of the nuclear data library in the SCALE Code System. In the processing pipeline, continuous-energy libraries are generated through a multi-step procedure, including point-wise cross section reconstruction, Doppler broadening for the selected set of temperatures, and generation of probability tables. The resulting data are merged at the end of the process into an AMPX-format binary file. This supports the use of JEFF libraries by the SCALE Monte Carlo neutron transport tools such as KENO-VI or Shift.
- FUDGE [24], which is a nuclear data package that supports reading, viewing, modifying, writing and processing nuclear data in the GNDS format [25]. Traditionally, JEFF nuclear data libraries are provided in ENDF-6 format but currently more efforts are being devoted to deliver JEFF-4.0 in the GNDS format. FUDGE also provides feedback on the consistency of an evaluated file so that it is also applied as format verification tool.
- NJOY_ACE, which takes the NJOY resources from the previous stage to generate probability tables and creates the ACE-format continuous-energy cross section data at various temperatures. These files are suitable for Monte Carlo transport simulations, facilitating high-fidelity reactor physics, shielding, and criticality safety analyses.
- OpenMC [26], which converts the ACE-format file to the HDF5 format that is used by the Monte Carlo code OpenMC. The HDF5 format enables efficient memory usage and fast data access during simulation. Datasets at different temperatures are produced but TSL data is not yet processed.
- PREPRO [27], which is used to generate group-wise cross section for FISPACT-II [28] activation-transmutation software in GENDF-1102 format. This routine also takes files prepared by means of NJOY in the previous stage and it is supported by the subsequent **verification** stage. ENDFtk is applied to ensure the consistency of the GENDF-1102 format dataset.

The generation of the resources required for the NEA JANIS software [29] has also been implemented recently. NJOY and PREPRO are applied in the **JANIS processing** stage to create the HENDF (Hybrid ENDF) files, readable and manageable by JANIS software. HENDF-format files include continuous-energy reconstructed cross sections in consistency with covariance data when available in BOXER format, plus all the remaining data included in the original evaluated file.

The pipeline has also been extended with covariance matrices generation, both in BOXER and COVERX formats. On the one hand, NJOY is used to process covariances of the average number of neutron per fission (MF31), covariances of neutron cross sections (MF33), covariances for angular distributions of secondary particles (MF34), and covariances for energy distributions of secondary particles (MF35). Evaluated files are inspected to determine the availability of covariances and then the NJOY/ERRORR and COVR modules are applied to produce BOXER-format covariance matrices. On the other hand, AMPX is applied to produce COVERX covariance datasets by means of the PUFF module.

When the nuclear data processing utilities are completed, the artifacts are collected and arranged in downloadable files. However, for a more efficient memory usage, selected datasets are deployed to package registry and they are stored under GitLab *tags* towards a proper version control. Among these packages, ACE-, AMPX-, DRAGLIB-, OpenMC- and GENDF-format files are retrieved along with outputs from format verification utilities, PENDF and HENDF files, and screen output for FUDGE. The evaluated files are also collected to provide a larger overview of the library version deployed.

4. JEFF-4.0 OFFICIAL PRODUCTS

As a result of the improved infrastructure development for the data and code pipeline supporting the JEFF project, the JEFF-4.0 library official release was accompanied by a variety of nuclear datasets, publicly available at [5].

The neutron-induced cross section evaluation packages are provided along with the ACE-format continuous-energy cross section data at several temperatures (293.6, 300, 600, 900, 1200, 1500, and 1800K), the PENDF point-wise cross section data at 0 K and 293.6 K, the HDF-5 continuous-energy cross section

data at the temperatures of the ACE-files, and the GENDF-1102 group-wise cross section data. These packages enable the use of the JEFF-4.0 nuclear data library by various Monte Carlo codes such as MCNP, Serpent, OpenMC, or FLUKA as well as the activation-transmutation code FISPACT-II. The TSL sub-library is also accompanied by the ACE-format continuous-energy cross section data at all the available temperatures. AMPX, DRAGLIBS and HENDF resources are not yet officially published since benchmarking activities are underway to support the quality assurance process. Likewise, covariance data is still subject to review before releasing them.

Both the JEFF-4.0 library contents and the NEA processing pipeline packages are now supported by a new research data management (RDM) platform based on the open-source Invenio RDM framework [30]. Invenio is a scalable solution with built-in, interoperable features developed by an international collaboration led by the Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire (CERN) [31]. At the heart of this platform are persistent digital identifiers that ensure data can be found, cited and traced in a manner that allows the interconnections between data resources, researchers, benchmarks and verification processes to be rigorously preserved. Each dataset, software package, virtual computing environment or other related resource is given a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) that enables users to reference the precise version and digital resource used in downstream applications including calculations and publications. Unique identifiers for organizations using the Research Organization Registry (ROR) connect data to the institutions that own and/or contribute, and Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID) integration allows individual researchers to be properly cited for transparency and crediting contributions. These features not only provide the basis for transparency and recognition but align the nuclear data community with international standards in open science.

The NEA Data Bank RDM platform provides machine-readable Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) that enable researchers and engineers to programmatically query, retrieve and reference data. Compared to legacy distribution methods, these interfaces are also persistent and allow users to integrate NEA datasets directly into their own workflows with confidence. This shifts the functionality of Data Bank services to allow interoperable and programmatic data use that is the foundation for machine learning and AI pipelines.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The JEFF-4.0 nuclear data library has largely benefited from enhanced support from the NEA Data Bank. The adoption of a GitLab-based DevOps environment facilitated the process towards the final library release, ensuring data preservation, transparency, and traceability. To align with the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles, the Data Bank has dedicated substantial efforts to modernize the data infrastructure regarding the evaluation, processing, verification and validation, and distribution of nuclear data. As a result, a processing pipeline has been developed to enable the use of JEFF-4.0 nuclear data library by a variety of codes. This pipeline is under continuous development, and further capabilities concerning validation and verification will be incorporated to the pipeline following up previous efforts at NEA Data Bank [32].

The NEA Data Bank has launched a new data management platform, where JEFF resources are published following the FAIR principles. This platform is also intended to provide access to scripts, intermediary results, reference calculations, full containerized environments, software source codes, and computational models used throughout the validation and verification process. Overall, the adoption of GitLab-based DevOps workflows, launch of the NEA Invenio RDM platform and integration of these systems as demonstrated with the JEFF-4.0 data project release marks a milestone in the transformation of the NEA Data Bank and its approach to data management. By combining the rigorous scientific communities of experts convened by the NEA through modern technology tools and data management practices, the NEA is creating a modern, transparent, interoperable, and trusted system for nuclear data, software, and benchmarks.

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